

ISSN 2181-9130

Doi Journal 10.26739/2181-9130

ҲУҚУҚИЙ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР ЖУРНАЛИ

9 ЖИЛД, 10 СОН

ЖУРНАЛ ПРАВОВЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

ТОМ 9, НОМЕР 10

JOURNAL OF LAW RESEARCH

VOLUME 9, ISSUE 10

ТОШКЕНТ-2024

ҲУҚУҚИЙ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ ПРАВОВЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ | JOURNAL OF LAW RESEARCH

№10 (2024) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.26739/2181-9130-2024-10>

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**MILESTONES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF LEGAL FRAMEWORKS FOR
CYBERSECURITY COOPERATION: FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF DIFFERENT
COUNTRIES AND ORGANIZATIONS**

For citation: Nosirov Barkhayot Murodjonovich. MILESTONES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF LEGAL FRAMEWORKS FOR CYBERSECURITY COOPERATION: FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF DIFFERENT COUNTRIES AND ORGANIZATIONS Journal of Law Research. 2024, 9 vol., issue 10, pp. 103-109

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14049332>

ANNOTATION

This article explores a comprehensive overview of the evolution of legal frameworks for cybersecurity cooperation, focusing on key developments from the 1990s to the present. It begins by exploring the early recognition of cybersecurity issues by the United Nations (UN) in the 1990s, highlighting the establishment of the UN Group of Governmental Experts (UN GGE) in 1999, which laid the groundwork for international collaboration on cyber security and governance. The adoption of the Council of Europe's Budapest Convention in 2001 marked a significant milestone, offering the first comprehensive legal framework for addressing cybercrime through international cooperation and harmonized national laws. It also discusses recent advancements in legal frameworks, such as the European Union's NIS Directive and Cybersecurity Act, which aim to strengthen cybersecurity across member states, and the United States' recent executive orders, which address the evolving cybersecurity threat landscape. It concludes by emphasizing the ongoing challenges and the need for adaptive and robust legal frameworks to effectively mitigate cyber risks in an increasingly interconnected world.

Keywords: ENISA, UN GGE, cyber security, CCDCOE, NIS, UN, legal framework.

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**KIBERXAVFSIZLIK SOHASIDA HAMKORLIKNING HUQUQIY ASOSLARINI ISHLAB
CHIQUISHDAGI MUHIM BOSQICHLAR: TURLI MAMLAKATLAR VA
TASHKIOTLAR NUQTAI NAZARIDAN**

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada 1990-yillardan to hozirgi kungacha bo'lgan kiber sohadagi asosiy o'zgarishlarga e'tibor qaralib, kiberxavfsizlik bo'yicha hamkorlikning huquqiy asoslari evolyutsiyasining to'liq

ko'rinishi keltirilgan. U 1990-yillarda Birlashgan Millatlar Tashkiloti (BMT) tomonidan kiberxavfsizlik muammolarining ilk bor tan olinishini o'rganishdan boshlanadi deb ko'rsatilgan. 1999-yilda kiberxavfsizlik va boshqaruv bo'yicha xalqaro hamkorlikning debochasi bo'lgan BMT Hukumat ekspertlari guruhi (UNGGE) tashkil etilgani maqolada alohida ta'kidlangan. 2001-yilda Yevropa Kengashining Budapesht konventsiyasining qabul qilinishi, xalqaro hamkorlik va uyg'unlashtirilgan milliy qonunlar orqali kiberjinoyatchilikka qarshi kurashning birinchi keng qamrovli huquqiy asosini yaratgan muhim bosqich sifatida ko'rsatiladi. Shuningdek, u a'zo davlatlarda kiberxavfsizlikni kuchaytirishga qaratilgan Yevropa Ittifoqining kiberxavfsizlik bo'yicha direktivasi va kiberxavfsizlik to'g'risidagi qonuni va kiberxavfsizlik tahdidlarining o'zgaruvchan manzarasini hal qiluvchi so'nggi AQSh hukumatining huquqiy hujjatlari keltirib chiqargan huquqiy asoslardagi so'nggi o'zgarishlarni muhokama qiladi. Shuningdek, tobora globallashib borayotgan dunyoda, kiber jinoyat tahdidiga kurashishda moslashuvchan va mustahkam huquqiy bazalar yaratishga bo'lgan ehtiyojni ta'kidlash bilan xulosa qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: ENISA, UN GGE, kiberxavfsizlik, CCDCOE, NIS, BMT, huquqiy asos.

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ВЕХИ В РАЗВИТИИ ПРАВОВЫХ ОСНОВ СОТРУДНИЧЕСТВА В ОБЛАСТИ КИБЕРБЕЗОПАСНОСТИ: С ТОЧКИ ЗРЕНИЯ РАЗНЫХ СТРАН И ОРГАНИЗАЦИЙ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Аннотация: В этой статье рассматривается всесторонний обзор эволюции правовых рамок сотрудничества в области кибербезопасности, с упором на ключевые события с 1990-х годов по настоящее время. Она начинается с изучения раннего признания проблем кибербезопасности Организацией Объединенных Наций (ООН) в 1990-х годах, подчеркивая создание Группы правительственных экспертов ООН (ГПЭ ООН) в 1999 году, которая заложила основу для международного сотрудничества в области кибербезопасности и управления. Принятие Будапештской Конвенции Совета Европы в 2001 году ознаменовало собой важную веху, предложив первую всеобъемлющую правовую основу для борьбы с киберпреступностью посредством международного сотрудничества и гармонизированных национальных законов. В ней также обсуждаются последние достижения в правовых рамках, такие как Директива ЕС о кибербезопасности и Закон о кибербезопасности, которые направлены на укрепление кибербезопасности в государствах-членах, и недавние исполнительные указы Соединенных Штатов, которые касаются меняющегося ландшафта угроз кибербезопасности. В заключение подчеркивается наличие текущих проблем и необходимость адаптивных и надежных правовых рамок для эффективного снижения рисков во все более глобальном мире.

Ключевые слова: ENISA, UN GGE, кибербезопасность, CCDCOE, NIS, ООН, правовые рамки.

The rapid spread of information and communication technologies (ICTs) has revolutionized modern society but has also introduced significant security challenges. As cyber threats become increasingly complex and global, the development of legal frameworks for cybersecurity cooperation has become a critical issue. This article examines key milestones in the evolution of such frameworks from a western perspective, focusing on national, regional, and international efforts to establish robust legal norms for cybersecurity cooperation. This article presents the history and progress in respect of legislation in fostering cooperation in cyber security.

The Early Years: Emergence of Cybersecurity Concerns in the 1990s United Nations Initiatives

The decade of the 1990s marked the beginning of a move that would seek to embrace cybersecurity as an emerging global governance issue. Cyber offences entailing an infringement of international interests were taken up by the UN, which included a few attempts in their reports to address the understanding of the impact of cyber threat on states and international order.

In 1999, the UN Group of Governmental Experts (UN GGE) on Developments in the Field of Information and Telecommunications in the Context of International Security was formed. The GGE marked one of the first multilateral efforts to address security issues in cyberspace and laid the foundation for subsequent cooperation.[1]

Adoption of the Information Security Doctrine of Russian Federation (2000)

The Russian Federation established a foundational approach to cybersecurity with the adoption of the Information Security Doctrine in 2000. This document outlined Russia's strategic vision for securing its information space, highlighting the protection of state information resources and the development of a national cybersecurity infrastructure as key priorities. The doctrine laid the groundwork for subsequent legislative and policy measures aimed at safeguarding Russia's digital sovereignty and addressing emerging cyber threats.[2]

The Council of Europe's Budapest Convention (2001)

One of the first and most significant legal instruments aimed at combating cybercrime is the Council of Europe Convention on Cybercrime, commonly known as the Budapest Convention, adopted in 2001. This treaty remains the cornerstone of international cooperation in the fight against cybercrime and sets out principles for harmonizing national laws on cybercrime, ensuring cross-border cooperation and simplifying extradition procedures.[3]

Building National Cybersecurity Strategies: 2000–2010

The United States: The National Strategy to Secure Cyberspace (2003)

Following the September 11 attacks, the United States recognized the vulnerability of its critical infrastructure to cyberattacks. In 2003, the United States released the National Strategy for Securing Cyberspace, which outlined a framework for protecting cyberspace through public-private partnerships, information sharing, and promoting international cooperation on cyber defense.[4]

The European Union's Cybersecurity Strategy (2004)

The European Union (EU) is actively developing a legal framework for cybersecurity. The European Network and Information Security Agency (ENISA) of 2004 was one of the first institutions dedicated to cybersecurity and has played a key role in supporting EU Member States in developing holistic cyber resilience strategies.[5]

The Global Response: The Rise of Multilateral and Regional Cooperation (2010–2020)

NATO's Cooperative Cyber Defence Centre of Excellence (CCDCOE)

In 2008, NATO established the CCDCOE in Tallinn, Estonia, to improve mechanisms for cooperative defence against cyber threats. The center has become the focal point for NATO cooperation in cyber security, helping to develop legal and operational strategies to protect member states from cyber attacks.[6]

Russia's Proposal for an International Cyber Treaty (2011)

In 2011, Russia proposed an international treaty on cybersecurity, emphasizing the need for a global approach to countering cyber threats. The proposal, presented to the UN, called for the establishment of binding international norms of state behavior in cyberspace, with a particular focus on preventing cyber warfare and the use of information technology for hostile purposes. Although the proposal did not receive widespread support, it underscored Russia's position on establishing international legal norms for cybersecurity.[7]

The Tallinn Manual (2013)

As cyber attacks on states have become more frequent, particularly in the context of military operations, the need for a legal framework to address cybersecurity issues in the context of international law has become apparent. The Tallinn Manual on International Law Applicable to Cyber Warfare, first published in 2013, was a significant academic work that attempted to apply existing principles of international law to the realm of cyber conflict.[8]

Strengthening Legal Norms and Frameworks: UN GGE and Normative Agreements (2015–2020)

United Nations Group of Governmental Experts (2015)

The 2015 UN GGE report was a milestone as it set out a set of voluntary norms for responsible state behavior in cyberspace. The report stressed the importance of states refraining from attacks on critical infrastructure and highlighted the need for capacity building in less developed countries to improve cybersecurity.[9]

Paris Call for Trust and Security in Cyberspace (2018)

Launched in 2018, the Paris Call was a multilateral initiative aimed at strengthening international cooperation on cybersecurity. It called for the protection of critical infrastructure, intellectual property, and electoral processes, and emphasized the need for international legal cooperation to reduce cyber risks.[10]

Russian Proposal for a UN Cybercrime Treaty (2019)

In 2019, Russia successfully led efforts by the UN General Assembly to establish an ad hoc committee tasked with drafting a new international cybercrime treaty. The initiative aims to create a comprehensive legal framework to combat cybercrime that is distinct from the Council of Europe's Budapest Convention, which Russia has not ratified. The proposed treaty aims to address issues such as cyber espionage, the use of information technology for criminal purposes, and the need for international cooperation in investigating and prosecuting cybercrime.[11]

Contemporary Challenges and Evolving Frameworks: 2020 and Beyond

European Union's NIS Directive and Cybersecurity Act (2019)

The EU has taken several landmark legal measures to strengthen its position in the field of cybersecurity. The Networks and Information Systems (NIS) Directive, adopted in 2016 and fully implemented by 2019, was the first pan-European cybersecurity law, requiring Member States to improve their national cybersecurity capabilities and cooperation.[12] In addition, the EU Cybersecurity Act, adopted in 2019, expanded the mandate of ENISA and introduced a framework for the certification of ICT products and services.[13]

United States' Cybersecurity Executive Orders and the Cyberspace Solarium Commission (2020)

The United States has also updated its legal framework to address the growing cybersecurity threat. In 2021, an executive order was signed to improve the country's cybersecurity, focusing on improving information sharing between the private sector and government entities, establishing stronger security standards, and encouraging the adoption of multi-factor authentication.[14]

The Cyberspace Solarium Commission, created in 2019, was tasked with developing a comprehensive strategy to defend the United States against cyber threats. Its 2020 report offered more than 80 recommendations, including strengthening international cooperation and revising laws to hold hostile state actors accountable for cyberattacks.[15]

ASEAN Regional Framework on Cybersecurity (2021)

In 2021, the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) adopted a comprehensive regional framework to enhance cybersecurity cooperation among its member states. This framework focuses on building capacity, improving information sharing, and promoting the adoption of international norms and standards. It underscores ASEAN's commitment to addressing cybersecurity challenges collectively and serves as a model for regional cooperation.[16]

National Strategies and Legislative Enhancements

Russian National Cybersecurity Strategy (2021)

In 2021, Russia released a new National Cybersecurity Strategy, outlining its priorities for securing the national digital environment. This strategy emphasizes the importance of protecting critical information infrastructure, combating cybercrime, and countering external threats to Russia's information space. It also highlights the need for international cooperation based on respect for state sovereignty and the principles of non-interference in domestic affairs, reflecting Russia's long-standing emphasis on digital sovereignty.[17]

U.S. Cybersecurity Executive Orders and Legislation (2021–2023)

The United States continued to strengthen its cybersecurity framework through several executive orders and legislative actions. In 2021, President Biden signed an executive order to improve the nation’s cybersecurity, which included mandates for federal agencies to raise security standards, adopt a zero trust architecture, and improve software supply chain security.[18] The Critical Infrastructure Cyber Incident Reporting Act (CIRCA), enacted in 2022, requires critical infrastructure entities to report significant cyber incidents to the Cybersecurity and Infrastructure Security Agency (CISA), thereby enhancing the country’s ability to respond to and mitigate cyber threats.[19]

Japan’s Revised Basic Law on Cybersecurity (2022)

In 2022, Japan revised the Basic Law on Cybersecurity to address emerging threats and align with global best practices. The revised law strengthens cybersecurity governance in Japan by enhancing the role of the National Cybersecurity Incident Preparedness and Strategy Center (NISC), promoting public-private partnerships, and advancing international cooperation.[20] This legislation reflects Japan's proactive approach to enhancing national cybersecurity resilience and its commitment to international cybersecurity norms.

Emerging Global Cybersecurity Challenges and Responses Cybersecurity and Geopolitical Tensions

The period 2021-2024 saw an increase in geopolitical tensions manifesting in cyberspace, particularly in the context of state-sponsored cyber operations targeting critical infrastructure. These actions highlighted the need for robust legal frameworks and international agreements to regulate state behavior in cyberspace. In response, several countries called for clearer definitions and stronger enforcement of international law in cyberspace, emphasizing the urgency of establishing binding norms and mechanisms to manage cyber conflicts.[21]

Regulating Emerging Technologies

As emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI) and quantum computing have begun to play a more prominent role in cybersecurity, legal frameworks have struggled to keep pace. The EU Artificial Intelligence Act proposed in 2021 and subsequent discussions in 2023 to regulate the cybersecurity implications of quantum technologies illustrate ongoing efforts to address the intersection of technological innovation and cybersecurity governance. These regulatory initiatives are critical to ensuring that the development and deployment of new technologies do not exacerbate cyber risks.

With the rapid development of emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence and quantum computing, Russian Federation has also sought to update its legal and regulatory frameworks to address the new challenges these technologies pose to cybersecurity. The government has initiated discussions on regulating AI-driven cybersecurity tools and the potential risks associated with quantum computing, signaling its intent to stay ahead of the curve in managing technology-related security risks.[22]

Future Directions and Challenges

Looking ahead, the continued evolution of cyber threats and the increasing integration of digital technologies into all aspects of society will require more dynamic and adaptable legal frameworks. Strengthening international cooperation, expanding public-private partnerships, and developing comprehensive policies that take into account the cybersecurity implications of new technologies will be essential to maintaining global security and stability in cyberspace.

The rapid development of information and communication technologies (ICTs) has transformed modern society, but it has also created complex security challenges that require robust and dynamic legal frameworks. This article traces the development of such a framework from a Western perspective and highlights important milestones in national, regional, and international efforts to establish norms and rules for cybersecurity cooperation. From the early recognition of cybersecurity as an international issue in the 1990s to the development of sophisticated national strategies and multilateral agreements in recent years, progress in promoting a collaborative global cybersecurity environment is clear.

Initiatives initiated by the United Nations, the Council of Europe, the European Union, NATO, and individual states such as the United States and Russia have made significant contributions to shaping the cybersecurity legal environment. The Budapest Convention, the Tallinn Principles, and various national strategies adopted over the past two decades demonstrate the increasing recognition of the need for coordinated, legally binding measures to combat cyber threats.

As cyberattacks become more sophisticated and the geopolitical landscape more complex, the importance of adaptable and forward-looking legal frameworks cannot be overstated. The international community faces a dual challenge: mitigating existing cyber risks while anticipating the impacts of new technologies such as artificial intelligence and quantum computing. Strengthening international cooperation, encouraging public-private partnerships, and ensuring that legal frameworks remain flexible and responsive to new challenges will be critical to creating a secure and resilient global digital environment.

Future efforts should focus on creating a comprehensive and inclusive international legal framework that recognizes the evolving nature of cyber threats and encourages responsible state behavior in cyberspace. The global community can work toward a more stable and secure digital future by leveraging existing agreements and continuing to innovate legal and policy approaches.

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ISSN 2181-9130

Doi Journal 10.26739/2181-9130

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ТОМ 9, НОМЕР 10

JOURNAL OF LAW RESEARCH

VOLUME 9, ISSUE 10

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